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STUDENT ATTITUDES TO PROFESSIONAL SKILLS TRAINING: ARE THEY MORE DIFFICULT TO LEARN IN A UNIVERSITY CONTEXT THAN TECHNICAL SKILLS?

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ABSTRACT

Here we explore undergraduate perceptions of different skills in two large-scale programmes in Australia and the UK. We have preliminary findings from an on-going study on the ways in which students believe they can best develop professional skills. We take a qualitative approach to a single optional, open-ended question at the end of the survey, which asks for "...any other comments". Just over 12% of a total of 1097 survey respondents filled out the question. We explore the themes through the lens of William Perry's (1981) schema of intellectual development with the addition of the concept of epistemic frames. We suggest that Professional Skills and Technical Skills may be perceived by students from different epistemic frames. Whilst students may develop more sophisticated epistemologies in relation to some areas of their study, they do not always transfer these framings to Professional Skills.

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1 INTRODUCTION

1.1 Study and Aims

In recent decades there has been a drive to prepare undergraduate students for professional practice, often with the inclusion of professional skills training in engineering curricula [1] [2] [3]. Professional skills usually encompass such skillsets as teamworking, communications, leadership and management, entrepreneurship, independent (and lifelong) learning, critical thinking, creativity to name a few. All are composite attributes and skills that are hard to define, dependent on context, and tend toward lifelong development, features that lead Knight (2007) to describe them as ‘wicked competences’ [4].

Here we report preliminary findings from a larger study that seeks to understand student perceptions of how they learn technical and professional skills. The drive to understand more, particularly about students attitudes to training in professional skills, was instigated by diverse responses to professional skills provision in two universities that interweave problem-based learning (PBL) activities, with skills training and more traditional forms of engineering tuition.[5] Each institution takes in a large cohort of undergraduates in excess of 750 students annually and provides a number of two-hour taught workshops to support skills development that run alongside work experience or university projects. At UCL skill support workshops are concentrated in the first two years of the degree programs, while in University of Sydney (UoS) activities are spread throughout all undergraduate years.[6][7]

In order to probe the reasons for the wide range of student responses to professional skills training, we have conducted a quantitative survey consisting of 6 structured questions, that ask participants about where they have developed or believe they should develop different competences, from technical to professional. Here we focus on an optional, open-ended question at the end of the survey, which asks, “Do you have any other comments on the competencies and skills you have (or haven’t) learnt at University, or anything else that you might be helpful to us in understanding your views and experiences?”. We included this question in order to tease out some of the attitudinal qualities that students hold regarding their educational development. Here we treat these questions qualitatively. Our aim is to gain a more nuanced understanding of the quality of students’ views and experiences that underlie the wide variation of responses to university professional skills training.

1.2 Background

“What can you do with such unaveragable judgements as ‘This course has changed my whole outlook on education and life. Superbly taught! Should be required of all students!’ and ‘This course is falsely advertised and dishonest. You have cheated me of my tuition!’?”. [8 p76-77]

So begins William G Perry’s explication of a schema for intellectual development. It was natural then, to look to Perry in the midst of similarly divergent responses to our own professional skills training provision. Using qualitative data from unstructured interviews recorded over a number of years, Perry devised a four-stage model of epistemological development in young adults. Each one of Perry’s stages is characterised by a typical attitude to knowledge. At one end ‘Dualism’ describes a position in which knowledge is either right or wrong, good or bad, but it is known by Authorities (eg: teachers, experts) that are external to the self. From here uncertainties begin to creep in, others have different opinions, even Authorities have different opinions. ‘Multiplicity’ describes a stage in which a diversity of opinion and values is acknowledged, but it is in areas where Authorities don’t yet know and opinions are all equal. ‘Relativism’ is a point at which opinions can be backed by evidence, sound argument, data, logic or rhetoric or not. Knowledge is relative and contingent. Now it is possible to use critical reasoning to make judgements between useful and worthless opinions. Finally, ‘commitment’ describes the individual affirmation of particular opinions, values and viewpoints achieved via the awareness developed through relativism. At this point, the student is able to think in ways that mirror the Authority and is able to construct knowledge internally.

A number of studies in engineering education have utilised Perry’s schema to explore student development and find ways to support it. Research on student development in the context of PBL, project-based learning (PjBL) and design-based learning is generally very encouraging in demonstrating the value of active learning in supporting and promoting intellectual development [9] [10] [11] [12] [13] [14]. (For simplicity in this short paper, we use the term PBL to refer to all PBL, PjBL and design-based activities.) Other work that looks specifically at student perceptions of their progress in developing a number of professional skills has shown the value of experiential pedagogies and active learning in supporting growth, most notably Beagan et al (2019) report positive results [16]. Itani and Srour (2016) also report positive results, finding that senior undergraduates

value their training in professional skills as a result of understanding their importance in industry. Yet they found some of the value that these students attributed to these skills was partly due to their aspiration to enter managerial or administrative careers in which engineering was not a core activity [15].

The majority of studies (eg: [9],[10],[12],[13]) that utilise Perry's schema treat it as a progressive, uni-directional model in which individuals adopt one epistemological position at a time, working from the simplest to the most complex. Other authors, most notable Elby (2010) and Elby and Hammer (2010), have argued for a more nuanced view of a fragmented epistemology, in which it is possible to hold many different models of knowledge at once [18] [19]. So, it may be possible to hold dualistic views in one context (a lecture perhaps) but to move toward relativism when cued by the context of PBL activities. Gainsburg (2015) cites several studies that demonstrate the influence of context and knowledge domain [11] on epistemology. What this signifies is that progression in one knowledge domain, does not necessarily signify progression in all domains.

In addition, Schaffer (2009) introduced the idea of epistemic frames [19]. A frame is a filter through which individuals can make sense of experience [20]. Like a camera view finder it limits what is observed, or how a situation is interpreted. Individuals may shift their frame dependent on their context. An epistemic frame drives what is noticed as knowledge, and influences beliefs about the way knowledge is developed and validated. This may be important in the context of professional skill development given that professional skills are inherently more multifarious and subjective than some technical topics. If students approach this kind of knowledge with the same epistemic frame with which they understand engineering principles, then they may not notice professional skills as knowledge at all.

2 METHODOLOGY

Just over 12% of a total of 1097 survey respondents filled out the final open question at the end of our survey. Participants were undergraduates from years 1-4 of their degree programmes, about half the total came from each institution. They were invited by e-mail to take an on-line survey containing 6 structured quantitative questions and 1 open-ended question.

We analysed 133 responses to the question "Do you have any other comments on the competencies and skills you have (or haven't) learnt at University, or anything else that you might be helpful to us in understanding your views and experiences?" Treating this data as qualitative data, we used an approach based on an inductive 'grounded' theory [17]. Our initial reading revealed highly divergent responses from very positive to very negative of the kind that are cited by Perry (above). Using Perry as inspiration, we developed a set of themes that relate to the way these students understand epistemic Authority. From the first set of codes we were then able to detail finer grained categories representing sub-themes that feature recurrent qualities within the data.

All responses reporting negative effects of the pandemic were placed within a single code which was excluded from other codes. Any other responses that fitted into more than one theme were coded more than once.

3 RESULTS

Table 1 shows the frequencies of codes emerging from the final coding of 133 responses. Just under a quarter of the student responses revealed a positive attitude to their learning or experience. These comments ranged from simple affirmations such as, "All good" to more revealing comments such as "[Projects] ...helped a great deal in making it understandable as to why we have to learn certain things." However, two thirds of the sample presented negative views on student experience and learning. These breakdown into two themes, the largest and most complex of which includes student attitudes toward epistemic authority. These sub-themes represent common epistemologies across the cohort.

Given this is a qualitative study, the number of positive versus negative comments is not a significant finding, what is more interesting is the fact that negative comments across the two different cohorts contained some markedly similar qualities.

4 DISCUSSION

Many students reported that professional skills could only be learned in the workplace, for example - "There is no way to consistently equip students with such a toolkit from drilling theory into their heads. Squeezing your way into the workplace and learning from there experience is the best way to gather such knowledge in my opinion." For this student the 'true authority' for

professional skills is in industry *and* these skills cannot be learned with theory. It is not clear whether this students frames theory as something that happens in university, but it is quite likely. In addition, this response highlights another main theme in which students perceive professional skills as emerging from experience or practice. For example, “I feel its a lost cause to try to formally teach professional skills and its best to just put students in situations where these skills can be developed naturally.” The first example cites learning from experience as the way to develop knowledge of professional skills and the second response takes it one stage further and believes these skills develop naturally given the right context (which is not formal teaching). Here professional skills are in an epistemic frame in which authority (university teachers and lecturers) is unhelpful, the only authority is experience or practice.

Table 1: Codes and Frequencies by % of Total Number of Responses

High Level Code	Frequency High Level % Total (n = 133)	Detailed Codes		Frequency as % Total (n = 133)
There is something Wrong with the Authority	56.4	True Authority is in Industry	Professional Skills	10.5
			Technical Skills	3
		Authority is Unnecessary	PS* is Only Learnt by Practice	12
			PS Cannot be Taught	3.8
		University Authority is Deficient	Professional Skills	37.6
			Technical Skills	15
		University Authority has Wrong Balance	More PS is needed	3
			More TS* is needed	4.5
Complaints and Demands	9.8	Complaints and Demands	Professional Skills	6
			Technical Skills	4.5
Development has Occurred (authority uncontroversial)	23	-	-	23
Pandemic issues (excluded from other codes)	12	-	-	12

* PS Professional Skills, TS Technical Skills

Many more students fell into a theme in which the university authority is in some way deficient. For example, one student describes professional skills training as “overall very disappointing because important learning opportunities such as conflict resolution and motivating teams to work together and succeed were overshadowed by a reluctance by staff to take affirmative action to address real issues.” Conflict resolution and motivation are both explored in this student’s curriculum, but the student apparently in a dualistic frame sees teaching staff as faulty for not being authoritative. This may be because the teamwork topics are covered in the context of a lecture, where the Authority show stands at the front and has all the knowledge. Yet, this knowledge was required by the student in a (different) PBL context. Whilst PBL scaffolds and cues may encourage the shift to a frame of Relativism, or even Commitment (see [12]), the teamwork support which was covered in a less active setting is still seen through a Dualistic frame.

A second student demonstrates a similar frame shift, “The problem is with the larger client projects, I am sure they are really helpful and really develop our professional skills but they are the most frustrating modules to complete. Due to some team members not caring about the module, client difficulties, not clear objectives.” The fact that dealing with difficult team members, clients and fuzzy objectives *are* professional skills has not occurred to this student. In this case, the deficiency is in the project, not specifically in the teaching staff. Nevertheless the frame is still somewhat dualistic, perhaps representing Perry’s description of a transition from Dualism to Multiplicity. Although the student acknowledges that professional skills develop within the context of the project, s/he has not been able to locate authority within the self. Authority is external, somewhere unfound and the cause much frustration.

A good example of the shift to Multiplicity is described by a student who divides knowledge in the following ways:

“The Sciences teach logical and rational thinking and is frequently associated with IQ, which is what most engineers are supposed to be good at (as maths is a core competency). In order to effectively teach professional competencies, interdisciplinary degrees that include arts, commerce and law subjects should be offered as these subjects are not maths based, are about people and require writing arguments from a multitude of perspectives and at times with no right and wrong answers. Unfortunately, the STEM way of thinking and the Arts/Commerce/Law way of thinking is almost always mutually conflicting, and some people might end up hating it, but it must be taught, as much as it is a pain in the neck to think in two different ways.”

Perry may describe this tactic as an avoidance or deflection of development. The realisation that knowledge is multiplicitous, contingent and/or constructed can cause much anxiety and he identifies various strategies, unconscious on the part of the individual, to hang on to the simple Dualistic notion of right or wrong and an Authority who knows which is which. What is inferred by this student is that the sciences are more Dualistic than the Arts and that s/he values the Sciences for this. Multiplicity in Arts, Commerce and Law is a ‘way of knowing’ that apparently conflicts with logical, rational science and for this student Multiplicity is clearly problematic. This may be a core issue for these students for whom the introduction of a highly relativist domain such as teamwork is provokes anxieties about having to think in different ways.

Finally, Perry describes a small number of students who deflect their own development by retreating to a Dualistic frame, or escaping with strong expressions of alienation. This small group he says, often lash out with “childlike complaints and demands” [8 p91]. We picked up a few responses in this vein ourselves. One student described professional skills training as “an unpleasant experience” while another reported “over pressured students prepared to lie cheat ... and basically do anything to achieve high marks...” and “lazy incompetent teachers more interested in their own research and ticking teaching expectations”. There is little to add to such a comment, except to feel some comfort from the fact that Perry reports similar responses from his own students.

This short paper raises the concept of epistemic frames as an influence on the ways in which student respond to professional skills training in our institutions. Some students who see this training as a negative addition to their programme may find it hard to incorporate professional skills in the same epistemic frame with which they see engineering. Engineering is factual, correct and logical, while professional skills are hard to define, fuzzy or ‘wicked’. The issue of Authority has been productive in the sense that it is mostly in relation to professional skills provision that these students find fault with Authority. It is notable that the frequency of negative responses to professional skills is higher across all of our codes with the exception of Complaints and Demands. We tentatively suggest that our high level and second level codes may represent epistemic frames and our job now is to further explore these framings with our students to confirm (or not) their existence.

REFERENCES

- [1] Winberg C, Bramhall M, Greenfield D, Johnson P, Rowlett P, Lewis O, Waldock J & Wolff K (2020) Developing employability in engineering education: a systematic review of the literature, *European Journal of Engineering Education*, 45:2, 165-180, DOI: 10.1080/03043797.2018.153408
- [2] Beagon Ú, Niall D & Ní Fhloinn E (2019) Problem-based learning: student perceptions of its value in developing professional skills for engineering practice, *European Journal of Engineering Education*, 44:6, 850-865, DOI: 10.1080/03043797.2018.1536114
- [3] Chance S, Williams B, Goldfinch T, Adams RS, Fleming LN (2019) Guest Editorial Special Issue on Using Enquiry- and Design-based Learning to Spur Epistemological and Identity Development of Engineering Students *IEEE Transactions on Education* 62(3): p157-164
- [4] Knight, P. (2007) *Fostering and Assessing 'wicked' competences* The Open University, Milton Keynes <https://docplayer.net/99662287-Fostering-and-assessing-wicked-competences.html>
- [5] Kadi A and Lowe D (2019) Diversity in student initial reactions to a Professional Engagement Program *AAEE Conference* https://aaee.net.au/wp-content/uploads/2020/07/AAEE2019_Annual_Conference_paper_85.pdf
- [6] Kadi A and Lowe D (2018) A new Professional Engagement Program – outline and initial outcomes. *AAEE Conference* <https://search.informit.org/doi/epdf/10.3316/informit.168596828760780>
- [7] Mitchell J, Nyamapfene A, Roach K, Tilley E (2019) Faculty wide curriculum reform: the integrated engineering programme *European Journal of Engineering Education* 46:1, 48-66, DOI: 10.1080/03043797.2019.1593324
- [8] Perry WG (1981) "Cognitive and Ethical Growth: The Making of Meaning" In Chickering AW *The Modern American College*. San Francisco: Jossey-Bass: 76-116
- [9] Pavelich MJ and Moore WS (1996) Measuring the Effect of Experiential Education Using the Perry Model *Journal of Engineering Education* 287-292
- [10] Marra RM, Palmer B, Litzinger T (2000) The Effects of a First-Year Engineering Design Course on Student Intellectual Development as Measured by the Perry Scheme. *Journal of Engineering Education* 39-45
- [11] Gainsburg J (2015) Engineering Students' Epistemological Views on Mathematical Methods in Engineering *Journal of Engineering Education* Vol 104 (2): pp139-166 DOI 10.1002/jee.20073
- [12] Zhu J, Liu R, Liu Q, Zheng T and Zhang Z (2019) Engineering Students' Epistemological Thinking in the Context of Project-based Learning *IEEE Transactions on Education* April 2019: 1-11
- [13] Rennick C, Hulls CCW and McKay KN (2019) Introductory Engineering Decision-Making: Guiding First-Year Students to Relativism in Software Design. *IEEE Transactions on Education* 62(3): 199-208. Retrieved from <https://doi.org/10.1109/TE.2019.2921273>
- [14] Bernhard J, Carstensen A, Davidsen J, Ryberg T (2019) Practical Epistemic Cognition in a Design Project-Engineering Students Developing Epistemic Fluency *IEEE Transactions on Education* 62(3): 216-225. <https://doi.org/10.1109/TE.2019.2912348>
- [15] Itani M and Srour I (2016) Engineering Students' Perceptions of Soft Skills, Industry Expectations, and Career Aspirations *Journal Professional Issues in Engineering Education and Practice* 142(1): 04015005-1 - 04015005-12

- [16] Beagon Ú, Niall D and Ní Fhloinn E (2019) Problem-based learning: student perceptions of its value in developing professional skills for engineering practice *European Journal of Engineering Education* 44(6): 850-865 DOI: 10.1080/03043797.2018.1536114
- [17] Glaser BG and Stauss AL (2000) *Discovery of Grounded Theory: Strategies for Qualitative Research* London. Aldine Transaction
- [18] Elby, A., & Hammer, D. (2010). Epistemological resources and framing: A cognitive framework for helping teachers interpret and respond to their students' epistemologies. In L. D. Bendixen & F. C. Feucht (Eds.), *Personal epistemology in the classroom: Theory, research, and implications for practice* (pp. 409–434). Cambridge, UK: Cambridge University Press.
- [19] Elby, A. (2010). Coherence vs. fragmentation in student epistemologies: A reply to Smith & Wenk. *Electronic Journal of Science Education*, 14(1). Retrieved from <http://ejse.southwestern.edu/article/view/7324/5618>
- [20] Shaffer, D. W., Hatfield, D., Svarovsky, G. N., Nash, P., Nulty, A., Bagley, E., . . . Mislevy, R. (2009). Epistemic network analysis: A prototype for 21st-century assessment of learning. *International Journal of Learning and Media*, 1(2), 33–53. doi:10.1162/ijlm.2009.0013